

Nuclear Energy: Nuclear Electricity and a Clean Environment

A. S. Mollah, A.Z.M. Salahuddin, A. Hossain, and J. Sied

Department of Nuclear Science and Engineering
Military Institute of Science & Technology, Mirpur Cantonment, Dhaka-1216.

1. Introduction

Increasingly, Bangladesh has become a nation of electricity users. At the same time, our nation is committed to preserve the environment. We must protect our clean air, environment, lakes and streams while providing ample supplies of energy. We must look to energy sources that are good for the environment-that don't cause urban smog or acid rain or emit the "greenhouse" gases that may cause global warming⁽¹⁻⁴⁾. Nuclear energy, for example. At present 435 commercial nuclear power units with total capacity of about 375 GW (e) are operated in the world (nearly 11 percent of the world's electricity as of February 2015, WNA website).

2. Environmental impact

No form of energy production or use is without environmental impact. The principal environmental impacts associated with nuclear power and sustainable development is air pollution/green house gas (GHG) emissions and radiation. Nuclear power plants produce electricity by the fissioning (Fig. 1) of uranium, not the burning of fuels. The most commonly used nucleus in nuclear power reactors is Uranium-235 or ^{235}U for short. The diagram below is a summary of what happens when a neutron collides with a ^{235}U nucleus and causes it to fission. The red balls are neutrons, the blue are ^{235}U , and the green are the smaller nuclei the ^{235}U splits into fission fragments. In a nuclear reactor, billions of fission events occur every second, so as a whole, a reactor can give us a lot of heat energy which we can then put to useful work. As a result, nuclear plants do not pollute the air with sulfur oxides, nitrogen oxides, dust or green house gases like carbon dioxide. Nuclear energy has helped create a cleaner environment throughout the world (Fig. 2). Nuclear energy plants eliminate 5 mil tons of sulfur oxides (Fig. 3) each year that would result if we produced that power by burning fossil fuels. Nuclear energy plants also eliminate 2 million tons of nitrogen oxide (NOx) emissions each year (Fig. 4). NOx contributes to the formation of urban smog as well as acid rain. Among the alternatives for generating electricity, fossil fuelled technologies (coal, oil and natural gas) have the highest CO₂ emission rates (Fig. 5) and create the majority of energy related GHG emissions⁽¹⁻⁴⁾. Fig. 6 presents a worldwide comparison, based on data from the United Nations Scientific Committee on the Effects of Atomic Radiation (UNSCEAR), showing, on a logarithmic scale, that the average radiation dose from nuclear power production is one ten-thousandth of the dose from natural background sources. As nation's demand for electricity grows, we must find a way to produce it without damaging our environment. Nuclear energy can help us meet this challenge-safely, cleanly, economically.

Fig. 1. Fission process of ^{235}U .

Fig. 2 Nuclear energy plants preserve vital natural resources- like clean air

Fig. 3. Sulfur oxide emissions from 1000 MW plant per year.

Fig. 4. Nitrogen oxide emissions from 1000 MW plant per year.

Fig. 5. Carbon dioxide emissions from 1000 MW plant per year.

Fig. 6. Worldwide average annual per capita dose from natural and anthropogenic radiation (adapted from UNSCEAR (2000)).

3. Nuclear Power Saves Lives

According to a study⁽¹⁾ global use of nuclear power has prevented about 1.84 million air pollution-related deaths and release of 64 billion tons of greenhouse gases that would have resulted from burning coal and other fossil fuels. The Table 1 shows the CO₂ emissions from each process in the nuclear power life cycle.

Table 1. CO₂ emissions from each process in the nuclear power life cycle.

gCO ₂ e/kWh	Front End	Construction	Operation	Back End	Decommission	Total
Minimum	0.58	0.27	0.1	0.4	0.01	1.36
Maximum	118	35	40	40.75	54.5	288.25
Mean	25.09	8.2	11.58	9.2	12.01	66.08
N	17	19	9	15	13	

From: http://www.nirs.org/climate/background/sovacool_nuclear_ghg.pdf

Pushker A. Kharecha and James E. Hansen of Columbia University⁽¹⁾ state that nuclear power has the potential to help control both global climate change and illness and death associated with air pollution. That potential exists, they say, despite serious questions about safety, disposal of radioactive waste and diversion of nuclear material for weapons. Concerned that the Fukushima accident in Japan could overshadow the benefits of nuclear energy, they performed an analysis of nuclear power's benefits in reducing carbon dioxide emissions and air pollution deaths.

4. Conclusion

Global use of nuclear power has prevented about 1.84 million air pollution-related deaths and release of 64 billion tons of greenhouse gases that would have resulted from burning coal and other fossil fuels, according to a paper in *Environmental Science & Technology*⁽¹⁾. As our nation's demand for electricity grows, we must find a way to produce it without damaging our environment & health. **Nuclear energy** can help us meet this challenge-safely, cleanly, economically.

References

1. Kharecha, P. A.; Hansen, J. E. Prevented mortality and greenhouse gas emissions from historical and projected nuclear power. *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 47 (2013), 4889–4895.
2. Benjamin K. Sovacool, Valuing the greenhouse gas emissions from nuclear power: A critical survey, *Energy Policy* 36 (2008) 2940–2953.
3. Lenzen, M.; [Frank Barnaby](#); James Kemp et al. (2008). "Life cycle energy and greenhouse gas emissions of nuclear energy: A review. *Energy Conversion and Management* 49, 2178-2199" (PDF). University of Sydney. Retrieved 2007-07-13.
4. Rashad, S.M., Hammad, F.H., Nuclear power and the environment: comparative assessment of environmental and health impacts of electricity generating systems. *Applied Energy* 65 (2000), 211–229.

Biography of Dr. Abdus Sattar Mollah & co-authors

Dr. A. S. Mollah is working as Professor at the Department of Nuclear Science and Engineering, MIST. He has authored or co-authored more than 150 peer reviewed international and national journals in the field of health physics, radioactive waste management, shielding calculation, radiation dosimetry, nuclear security and safeguards, accidental radiation dose analysis, medical dosimetry and regulatory control. He was the supervisor of about 30 M. Sc. students, 8 M. Phil. students and 7 Ph.D. students of different public universities. Key professional experiences of Prof. Mollah are:

Professor, Department of Nuclear Science and Engineering, MIST

Former Dean, Faculty of Science and Engineering, KYA University; Head, Department of Medical Physics, KYA University; Part-time Teacher, Department of Nuclear Engineering, Dhaka University; Part-time Teacher, Department of Bio-Medical Physics and Technology, Dhaka University; Part-time Teacher, Department of Physics, BUET; Member (Planning) and Chief Scientific Officer, Bangladesh Atomic Energy Commission (BAEC); Director, International Affairs Division and NLO for IAEA; Director, Nuclear Safeguards and Security Division, BAEC; Director, Nuclear Power and Energy Division, BAEC; Director, Nuclear Safety and Radiation Control Division, BAEC

Colonel Abu Zafor Mohammad Salahuddin

Dean, Faculty of Nuclear Science and Biomedical Engineering, MIST

Major Md Altab Hossain, PhD

Head, Department of Nuclear Science and Engineering, MIST

Former Faculty, Department of Mechanical Engineering, MIST; Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Malaya (UM), Malaysia; Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University Selangor (UNISEL), Malaysia

Jubair Sieed, MSc (Nuclear Engg.)

Assistant Professor, Department of Nuclear Science and Engineering, MIST